

PROGRAMME

8th BALKAN CONGRESS OF ARTHROSCOPY, SPORTS TRAUMATOLOGY & KNEE SURGERY

ORGANIZED BY BALKAN SOCIETY OF ARTHROSCOPY
SPORTS TRAUMATOLOGY AND KNEE SURGERY

HOTEL IZGREV

18-20
MAY
2017

MACEDONIA

STRUGA

welcome

Dear friends and colleagues,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee of the 8th Balkan Congress of Arthroscopy, Sports Traumatology and Knee Surgery, it is my honor to invite you to participate in the congress that will take place in Struga from 18th to 20th May 2017. It will be organized by the Balkan Association for Arthroscopy, Knee Surgery and Sports Traumatology.

The Congress will be an opportunity to present our achievements, previous experiences and innovations in the treatment of sports injuries, rehabilitation and prevention of the same. Arthroscopy is gaining impetus in the treatment of sports injuries and slowly conquers all joints (knee, shoulder, ankle, wrist radiokarpal joint, the hip joint).

Many prominent orthopedic surgeons from the region ranging from Croatia to Turkey will be present at this eighth congress of our association. Many well-known specialists in this field from the European countries are invited to participate in the congress.

Seven consecutive congresses have been organized so far and as you can see the arthroscopic surgery, surgery of the knee and shoulder, and ankle, are developed with a great pace and in some elements we can stand shoulder to shoulder with our colleagues from the developed European countries.

With respect,

Prof. Dr. Zlatko Temelkovski

Head of the University Clinic of Orthopedics - Medical Faculty Skopje

President of the Balkan Association for arthroscopy, sports traumatology and knee Surgery

Prof. dr. Asparuh Asparuhov
Dean of the Medical University in Pleven Bulgaria

Prof.dr.sc. Nikola Čičak
Deputy Manager of Akromion Croatia

Dr. David Dejour,MD, PhD
Clinique Emilie de Vialar, Lyon, France

Prof. dr. Mahmut Nedim Doral
Faculty member of the Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology at Hacettepe University Faculty of Medicine

Prof. Dr. Vladimir Martinek
Head of Department of Schön Klinik
Harthausen Joint Center

René Verdonk MD, MSc, MFPM, MBA, PhD
Emeritis Professor at Ghent University

Dr. Ricardo Varatojo
Coordinator of the Knee,Ankle,Arthroscopy and Sports Trauma Unit at Centro de Ortopedia,Hospital CufDescobertas,Lisbon,Portugal

invited lectures

INTERNATIONAL BOARD

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- Doral Mahmoud Nedim (Turkey)
- Manojlovic Slavko (BiH)
- Maznejkov Hristo (Bulgaria)
- Milankov Miroslav (Serbia)
- Papageorgiou Christos (Greece)
- Temelkovski Zlatko (Macedonia)
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THURSDAY /18 MAY 2017/

Moderators: Temelkovski Z. / Doral M.N. / Asparuhov A.

- 16:30 - 16:50 Meniscal replacement : indications technique and mid term results
René Verdonk MD, MSc, MFPM, MBA, PhD, Emeritis Professor at Ghent University
- 16:50 - 17:10 Allograft Men. Transplantation
Christos D Papageorgiou, University of Ioannina, Greece
- 17:10 - 17:30 Open –Wedge valgisation HTO, my approach
Dr. Ricardo Varatojo, Hospital CufDescobertas, Lisbon, Portugal
- 17:30 - 17:50 Unicondylar or HTO for the treatment of unicompartmental osteoarthritis?
Prof. Dr. Vladimir Martinek, Schön Klinik Harthausen Joint Center, Bad Aibling, Germany
- 17:50 - 18:10 Improving TKA mobility: Surgical techniques, implants, patient –or postoperative management
Dr. Ricardo Varatojo, Hospital CufDescobertas, Lisbon, Portugal
- 18:10 - 18:30 One - Stage vs. two - Stage revision in infected TKA
Dr. Ricardo Varatojo, Hospital CufDescobertas, Lisbon, Portugal.
- 18:30 - 18:50 Primary Repair of Late Achilles Tendon Ruptures Via Endoscopic Control
Prof. Dr. Mahmut Nedim Doral, Hacettepe University Faculty of Medicine, Ankara, Turkey
- 18:50 - 19:10 Quadriceps tendon lesion: reasons and treatment options
Prof. dr. Asparuh Asparuhov, Medical University in Pleven, Bulgaria
- 19:10 - 19:30 Shoulder arthroscopy: challenge and reality.
Prof. Dr. Viktor Kamilovski, PHI University Clinic for Surgical Diseases "St. Naum Ohridski-Skopje", Macedonia
- 20:30 Welcome Cocktail (Restaurant terrace)

DINNER

programme

LIGAMENT INJURIES

Moderators: Papageorgiu Ch. / Martinek V. / Maznejkov H.

- 09:00 - 09:15 The Chapter of ACL; Prevention or Surgery?
Prof. Dr. Mahmut Nedim Doral, Hacettepe University Faculty of Medicine, Ankara, Turkey
- 09:15 - 09:30 ACL all-inside technique. Can we get better?
Prof. Dr. Vladimir Martinek, Schön Klinik Harthausen Joint Center, Bad Aibling, Germany
- 09:30 - 09:45 ACL Surgery
Dr. Christo Maznejkov, General Hospital "St. Sofia", Sofia, Bulgaria
- 09:45 - 10:00 PCL rec. were we are TODAY
Christos D Papageorgiou, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece
- 10:00 - 10:15 Btb graft preparation technique to increase cross-sectional area of the graft in anterior cruciate ligamen reconstruction
*Milankov M, Obradovic M, Vranjes M, Bjelobrk M
Department of orthopedic surgery and traumatology, Clinical Center Vojvodina, Medical Faculty of Novi Sad, Serbia*
- 10:15 - 10:30 Our experience with hybrid tibial fixation in anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction
*Nataša J. J, Srđan N, Vladimir H, Oliver D, Vaso K, Milan S, Mirko O, Miroslav M
KCV, Clinic of orthopaedic surgery and tramatology Novi Sad, Serbia*
- 10:30 - 11:00 WORWAG PHARMA- SIMPOSIUM, *Prof. Dr. Zlatko Temelkovski*
- 11:00 - 11:30 Coffee Break

Moderators: Milankov M. / Andonovski A. / Trsek D.

- 11:30 - 11:40 What factors influence the final results of acl reconstructions?
*Ristic V, Maljanović M, Milankov M.
General Hospital Subotica, Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Serbia
Clinical Centre of Vojvodina, Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Serbia*

FRIDAY /19 MAY 2017/

- 11:40 - 11:50 ACL / PCL reconstruction: conventional vs "all inside" technique
Nestorovski Z., Petkov N.
Department of Orthopaedics and Traumatology, City General Hospital "8-th of September", Skopje, Macedonia
- 11:50 - 12:00 Revision ACL reconstruction - one or two stage surgery?
Andonovski A, Strezovski K, Andonovska B, Temelkovski Z.
University Clinic for Orthopedic Surgery, Traumatology, Anesthesiology and Intensive Care. Faculty of Medicine, University "Ss Cyril and Methodius", Skopje, Macedonia.
- 12:00 - 12:15 Success of repaired meniscus healing with and without anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction
Tršek D, Hašpl M
ACROMION, Hospital for Orthopaedic Surgery, Krapinske Toplice, Croatia
- 12:15 - 12:25 Congenital luxation of the patella
Dzoleva-Tolevska R, Doral MN, Poposka A, Samardziski M, Georgieva D, Jovanovski-Srceva M.
Surgery University Clinic for Orthopedic, Hacettepe University Hospital-Ankara, University Clinic for Anesthesia, Skopje, R. of Macedonia
- 12:25 - 12:55 BERLIN-CHEMIE SIMPOSIUM, *Prim. Dr. Krste Strezovski*
- 13:00 - 14:30 LUNCH *Lunch*

SHOULDER

Moderators: Cicak N. / Asparuhov A. / Martinek V.

- 14:30 - 14:45 Arthroscopic treatment of overhead athletes
Prof.dr.sc. Nikola Čičak
Hospital for Orthopaedic Surgery Akromion, Krapinske Toplice, Croatia
- 14:45 - 15:00 Arthroscopic repair of the partial supraspinatus and subscapularis tear
Prof.dr.sc. Nikola Čičak
Hospital for Orthopaedic Surgery Akromion, Krapinske Toplice, Croatia

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- 15:00 - 15:15 Posterior shoulder instability
Prof.dr.sc. Nikola Čičak
Hospital for Orthopaedic Surgery Akromion, Krapinske Toplice, Croatia
- 15:15 - 15:30 The Management of shoulder pain syndrome
Dr. Doru FILIPESCU, "Saint John", Bucharest, Romania
- 15:30 - 15:45 Anterior traumatic shoulder instability: reinsertion of a bankart lesion with suture anchors
Prof. dr. Asparuh Asparuhov, Medical University in Pleven, Bulgaria
- 15:45 - 16:00 Differential diagnosis and treatment of shoulder impingement
Prof. Dr. Vladimir Martinek, Schön Klinik Harthausen Joint Center, Bad Aibling, Germany
- 16:00 - 16:10 Arthroscopic bankart lesion repair using knotless soft tissue fixation
Petkov N, Nestorovski Z, Lazarevski P, Siskova I, Hristov M, Kostadinovski V
Department of Orthopaedics and Traumatology City General Hospital 8-th of September, Skopje, Macedonia
- 16:10 - 16:25 Endoscopic carpal ligament dissection via single proximal incision technique
Prof. dr. Asparuh Asparuhov, Medical University in Pleven, Bulgaria
- 16:25 - 16:35 Endoscopic carpal tunnel release (ECTR)
C. Asraf Nesant, I. Gkiatas, K. Mpellos D. Kosmas, C. D. Papageorgiou,
University Hospital of Ioannina, Ioannina Greece
- 16:35 - 16:45 Arthroscopic treatment of dorsal wrist ganglia
Kasapinova K, Kamiloski V.
General Hospital St. Naum Ohridski, Skopje, Macedonia
- 16:45 - 16:55 Shoulder surgery in sitting position –what could go wrong?
Jovanovski-Srceva M¹, Dzoleva R¹, Mojsova M¹, Nanceva J¹, Gavrilovska A¹, Kuzmanovska B¹, Jankulovski N²
¹Clinic for Traumatology, Orthopedics, Anesthesia, Reanimation, Intensive Care and Emergency, Skopje, Macedonia, ²Clinic for Abdominal Surgery, Skopje, Macedonia
- 16:55 - 17:05 COFFEE BREAK

FRIDAY /19 MAY 2017/

REHABILITATION

Moderators: Rumiana Taseva / Erieta D Nikolic / Tatjana Nozica Radulovic

- 17:05 - 17:35 DIETPHARM SIMPOSIUM - Rehabilitation in spine sport injuries
Prim. Dr. Tatjana NIKOLIC, Croatia
- 17:35 - 17:45 Innovative approach in physiotherapy after anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction
Rumiana Taseva - National Sports Academy "Vassil Levsky" - Physiotherapy Department, Sofia, Bulgaria
- 17:45 - 18:00 Effects of manual joint mobilization and mobilization with movement in the management of frozen shoulder
Dimitrova, E., NSA, Department of Physiotherapy, Sofia, Bulgaria
- 18:00 - 18:10 Knee rehabilitation in patients operated with allograft or autograft. When recovery is faster?
Kazalakova K. PhD, Andreev A. MD, Spassoff V. MD, Vlahova T. - Emergency Hospital "Pirogov", Sofia, Bulgaria
- 18:10 - 18:20 Fast-track approach in rehabilitation after knee arthroplasty
Tatjana Nozica - Radulovic, Dragana Dragicevic - Cvjetkovic, Jelena Stankovic, Petar Cvijic, Bojan Kuzmanovic, Institute of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation "Dr Miroslav Zotovic", Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- 18:20 - 18:30 Effects of extracorporeal shock wave therapy in treatment of musculoskeletal disorders
Nikolij D. Erieta - Institute of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Medical Faculty, Skopje, Macedonia
- 18:30 - 19:00 PLASMOLIFTING - SIMPOZIUM, Dr. V.Gerasimenko, Moscow, Russia
- 19:10 - 19:10 Rehabilitation after acl reconstruction-early findings
Kalchovska-Ivanovska B¹, N. Nastov², Manoleva M.¹, Gocevska M.¹, Koevska V.¹, Mitrevska B.¹, Savevska-Gerakaroska C.¹, Ivanovski M³ - ¹Institute of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Skopje, Macedonia; ²PHI UC for Surgical Diseases "St. Naum Ohridski", Skopje, Macedonia; ³KB Acibadem/Sistina Skopje, Macedonia
- 19:10 - 19:20 Six week rehabilitation program of ankle and foot injuries in athletes
Bojcheski O¹, Maleska Ivanovska V², H. Kica³, K. Kica³, Bojcheska M⁴, Ganiu F³, Stebleva S³, Galjak M, PHI Health Center Struga¹; Department of Physiology, Medical Faculty, Skopje²; Faculty of Physical Education, University of Tetovo³; Medical University of Pristina - K. Mitrovica⁵
- 19:20 - 19:30 Rehabilitation in patients with dhs surgically treated pertrochanteric fracture
*Mitrevska B¹, Poposka A², Nikolik- Dimitrova E¹, Koevska V¹, Gerakaroska-Savevska C¹, Gocevska M¹, Kalcovska- Ivanovska B¹, Manoleva M¹.
¹Institute of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, ²Clinic of Orthopedics, Skopje, Macedonia*
- 21:00 GALA DINNER

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SATURDAY /20 MAY 2017/

Moderators: V. Kamilovski / S. Trpevski / Z. Temelkovski

- 09:00 - 09:15 Classification and treatment of patellofemoral disorders
Dr. David Dejour, MD, PhD, Clinique Emilie de Vialar, Lyon, France
- 09:15 - 09:30 History of the trochlear dysplasia, why doing a trochleoplasty?
Dr. David Dejour, MD, PhD, Clinique Emilie de Vialar, Lyon, France
- 09:30 - 09:45 ACL reconstruction "menu carte" management of frozen shoulder
Dr. David Dejour, MD, PhD, Clinique Emilie de Vialar, Lyon, France
- 09:45 - 10:15 PHARMA GEN - SIMPOSIUM, *Prof. Dr. Milan Samardziski*
- 10:15 - 10:30 Trochlear dysplasia congenital or biomechanical development
Prof. Dr. Zlatko Temelkovski, University Clinic for Orthopedic Surgery, Skopje, Macedonia
- 10:30 - 10:45 Novel scaffold –based treatment in superior cartilage repair with microfracture
*C. Asraf Nesant, P. Ziara, A. Fylaktos, E. Papanastasiou, C. D. Papageorgiou
University Hospital of Ioannina, Ioannina Greece*
- 10:45 - 11:00 Surgical management of patellar fracture
*Trpeski S., Kaftandziev I., Arsovski O., Nikolov Lj., Hasani I., Mihajlova M.
University Clinic for Traumatology – Skopje, Macedonia*
- 11:00 - 11:10 Ilizarov apparatus in knee arthrodesis as a treatment option after infected total knee arthroplasty
*Lalić I, Kecojević V, Dulić O, Rašović P. Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Department of Orthopaedic
Surgery and Traumatology, Medical faculty, University of Novi Sad, Serbia*
- 11:10 - 11:20 Wrist arthroscopy: evolution, portals, arthroscopic wrist anatomy and indications
Kamiloski V. Kasapinova K. University Surgery Clinic "St. Naum Ohridski", Skopje, Macedonia
- 11:20 - 11:30 Wrist arthroscopy techniques in our practise
Kasapinova K, Kamiloski V. University Surgery Clinic "St. Naum Ohridski", Skopje, Macedonia
- 11:30 - 11:40 Insulin resistance in orthopedic surgical patients and its effect on orthopedic patients-review of literature
*Jovanovski-Srceva M¹, Dzoleva R¹, Kuzmanovska B¹, Kartalov A¹, Shosholceva M¹, Mojsova M¹,
Stavridis S², Jankulovski N³
¹Clinic for Traumatology, Orthopedics, Anesthesia, Reanimation, Intensive Care and Emergency,
Skopje, ²Clinic for Urology, Skopje, ³Clinic for Abdominal Surgery, Skopje, Macedonia*
- 11:40 - 11:50 Closed subtalar dislocation without associated fracture – a case report
Popovska D, Runcheva M, Puzderliski P, Ushinov K. - PHI Clinical Hospital Shtip, Macedonia
- 11:50 - 12:00 Comparison of adductor canal block with femoral nerve block in anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction
*Malinovska-Nikolovska L¹, Shirgoska B², Nestorovski Z¹, Manoleva M²
City General Hospital "8-mi Septemvri", Skopje, Medical Faculty, Skopje,*
- 12:00 **CLOSING CEREMONY**

FRIDAY / 19 MAY 2017/

**Moderators: Papageorgiou Christos / Milankov Miroslav / Maznejkov Hristo
Temelkovski Zlatko / Andonovski Alan / Iliev Boro / Nestorovski Zoran / Jovanovski Ilija**

16:00 - 18:00 Lectures

1. Equipment and instruments, *Prof. Dr. Zlatko temelkovski*
2. Anaesthesia in Arthroscopic Knee surgery, *Prof. Dr. Jaminka Nanceva*
3. Possibilities of the arthroscopic surgery of the knee, *Dr. Alan Andonovski*
4. Arthroscopic meniscal suture, *Dr. Denis Tršek*
5. Pathology of the lateral meniscus, *Prof. Dr. Zlatko Temelkovski*
6. Arthroscopic synovectomy of the knee joint, *Prof. Dr. Christos Papageorgiu*
7. Arthroscopy surgery with or without complication, *Prof. Dr. Miroslav Milankov*

18:00 - 20:00 Practical training

SATURDAY /19 MAY 2017/

**Moderators: Papageorgiou Christos / Milankov Miroslav / Maznejkov Hristo
Temelkovski Zlatko / Andonovski Alan / Iliev Boro / Nestorovski Zoran / Jovanovski Ilija**

10:00 - 12:00 Practical training

12:00 Awarding of certificates

arthroscopy course

ILIZAROV APPARATUS IN KNEE ARTHRODESIS AS A TREATMENT OPTION AFTER INFECTED TOTAL KNEE ARTHROPLASTY

Lalić I, Kecojević V, Dulić O, Rašović P.

Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Department of Orthopaedic Surgery and Traumatology, Medical faculty, University of Novi Sad.

Introduction: A chronic periprosthetic infection with attendant failure of the knee extensor mechanism is one of the most disastrous outcome following total knee arthroplasty and knee arthrodesis may be the last possible option treatment with the exception lower limb amputated. AIM: The aim of this study is to represent the results to achieve knee arthrodesis in patients with chronically septic total knee arthroplasty. Methods: In our retrospective study we reviewed the clinical record of 27 patients who were treated with Ilizarov circular external fixator for this condition. Male to female ratio was 13:14. Main age of the patients was 62,3 years. We used Cierny-Mader classification for the clinical and pathoanatomical assessment. For the assessment of the bone defect we used Engh classification.

Results: Complete union we had in 22 (81,4%) patients. Mean time for healing was 5,7 months, range (3-15). Mean residual limb shortness was 4,7 cm and mean follow-up was 21 months. We also had a five nonunion (18,6%) complications: three with septic intrarticular nonunion, two had intolerance to the Ilizarov apparatus, so we removed earlier.

Discussion and conclusion: The Ilizarov circular external fixator provides us a high rate of bone healing and low risk of septic dissemination in patients with infected total knee arthroplasty (TKA).